

Redefinitions of History in Digital Narration: Traces, Narrative Violence, and the Operativity of the False

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Abstract

This article examines how narration operates in digital environments and how this may reshape our contemporary conception of history. Treating social media as narrative spaces in which subjectivity and collective life are shaped, it argues that the contemporary informational problem exceeds epistemology. Through cases such as Trump's generative political propaganda, media tribunals, and AI-enabled non-consensual pornographic deepfakes, the article suggests that the issue is not merely the circulation of falsehood, but the capacity of narratives to become socially and historically operative even when detached from embodied, biographical, and historically situated traces. What emerges is a new and potentially violent narratability of lives, shaped by older logics of objectification, which compromises historical legibility and thus subjectivity itself.

Keywords: Narrative violence; digital narration; historical legibility; objectification; operativity of the false

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«When the design of my life is completed,
shall I, shall other people see a stork.»
(Blixen, 1937/1986, p. 269)

1. History as Narration and the Question of Traces

If we understand history as the set of human actions and traces, that is, in terms of what people have done, chosen, and enacted in relation to one another, then history can also be approached as narration. More precisely, while history refers here to the field of human actions, events, and traces, historiography concerns the writing of history, namely the critical selection, organization, and narration of those traces (Encyclopaedia Britannica, n.d.). In this sense, the question is not only what happens, but how what happens is narrated and made legible. For where there is narration, there are always subjects at stake. History concerns us deeply because it tells of us, situates us within time, and helps us to see and understand ourselves within the world we inhabit.

Considering social media as a narrative space, if narration ordinarily allows a life to become retrospectively legible through its traces, the digital question is what happens when narration becomes continuous, immediate, and externally rewritable before those traces can sediment into a readable form.

Narration, however, is always *ex post*: a story arises only once events have reached their conclusion and, having passed, become narratable, namely open insofar as they become legible and interpretable. Cavarero addresses this complexity through the well-known story of the stork taken from Isak Dinesen (Blixen, 1937/1986; Cavarero, 1997). In that story, a man looks out of his window in the early morning and sees that the footprints left by his movements during the previous night have formed the figure of a stork (Blixen, 1937/1986). The image was not intentional. It emerges only retrospectively, as a unified reading of actions that, while being performed, did not yet disclose their overall shape.

Through Cavarero, it becomes possible to see that a life story is ontologically irreducible to any fixed definition (Cavarero, 1997). Subjectivity is never isolated, but constitutively relational, insofar as the I presupposes a You, and for this very reason, no one fully possesses the meaning of their own story from within the immediacy of action (Cavarero, 1997). A life becomes narratable only retrospectively and in relation to others (Cavarero, 1997). The stork thus symbolizes biography as a figure that emerges from traces, and that may be more visible to others than to the one who lives it (Blixen, 1937/1986). For this reason, in order to answer

the question of who I am, someone must tell me my stork, namely my story, that describes me without defining me (Cavarero, 1997).

This also means that there will necessarily be a plurality of narrations, due to the interpretation, none of which can be perfectly identical (Cavarero, 1997). Between the story told by a victor and that told by the defeated, for instance, an abyss may open. Yet such plurality does not amount to arbitrariness, since what may differ is the meaning attributed to events, not the events themselves. Narrative form is suited to singular lives precisely because it remains unique, dynamic, specific, and responsive to their unfolding, while no single account should be allowed to exhaust the complexity of an existence (Cavarero, 1997).

2. Digital narration beyond the epistemological problem

It is important to emphasize that Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, X, etc., are linguistic and narrative places and, as such, performative spaces of power. Furthermore, digital environments have by now become a constitutive part of everyday life. Therefore, given that we inhabit the Fourth Revolution (Floridi, 2017), it becomes necessary to ask how the conception of story changes under digital conditions, what happens to narration when it is technologically mediated, and whether historical narration online is shaped by specific hegemonic forces, and if so, by whom.

If Blixen's stork names the retrospective form through which a life may begin to appear from its traces, digital environments seem to intensify the opposite condition: an eternal present in which subjects remain constantly immersed as agents and objects of narration, without the distance required to look back at their own footprints and let a shape emerge (Blixen, 1937/1986; Cavarero, 1997; Riva, 2018). In such a digital setting, where everyone can express opinions, the openness of narration, on the other hand, becomes newly vulnerable to intervention, such as manipulation, distortion, and rewriting (Riva, 2018). Paradoxically, this means that reality often becomes unreadable, generating deep confusion.

For instance, during Trump's second presidency AI-generated and altered imagery has repeatedly been used not simply to embellish communication, but to simplify complexity, solidify political symbolism, ridicule criticism, and impose socially operative frames: from the AI image of Trump as pope and then as Jesus Christ, to altered expansionist imagery draping Greenland in the U.S. flag, to AI-generated racial caricatures of political enemies such as Barack Obama, and even a video showing Trump dropping excrement on No-Kings protesters

(Duster, 2026; Hunnicutt et al., 2026; Mouriquand, 2025; Shalal, 2025; Swai, 2026). In each case, AI does not merely illustrate a pre-existing claim; it helps convert fantasy, mockery, aggression, and symbolic domination into highly circulable visual narration. These examples matter not as isolated scandals, but because they reveal a more general condition: narration now acquires force not by corresponding to lived reality, but by circulating effectively enough to shape perception and social consequence.

In this sense, Trump uses generative AI to stage himself within roles of symbolic authority he does not formally occupy, as pope, as judge, as king of the world, and thus to present not only what he is, but what he could do and what he claims the power to embody. The violence lies precisely in this imposition: such narration might acquire plausibility, become credible, and could be, voluntarily or involuntarily, socially accepted. What matters, then, is no longer verisimilitude alone, but operativity: the capacity of an image to travel, stick, wound, and reorganize perception even when its artificiality is evident (Giansiracusa, 2021).

Yet this is a new level of power entrusted to words and narration, one marked by unprecedented dimensions and extensions and by its capacity to invest our lives directly. Through social media, the word, which already in itself shapes reality through meaning (Butler, 2021; Foucault, 2009), acquires a form of contact that is at once direct and individual, and at the same time massive, since, in principle, anyone can express themselves and reach an exponentially growing number of people. For this reason, it is crucial to clarify the spatio-temporal structure of social media. These virtual relational spaces allow words to travel without geographical distance; information moves repeatedly and incessantly toward a potentially ever-growing number of users, that is, persons (Fabris, 2018).

What does this mean? It means that social media cannot be assimilated into newspapers or television. Although there remains a bodily and physical distance between persons, there is nonetheless a subtle invasion, insofar as it becomes increasingly impossible to distinguish the public sphere from the private one (Riva, 2018). Put differently, if one considers the logic of the feed, social media allows each expression, each piece of information, to reach the individual user instantaneously and repeatedly, in multiple forms and variations (Giansiracusa, 2021; Reed et al., 2021). On a large scale, one thus encounters a direct and singular relation. Transmission is therefore far more intense because it is intimate and proximate: content addresses each user directly, is “personalized,” and reaches someone who spends many hours a day, every day of their life, within these spaces (Fabris, 2018; Reed et al., 2021; Riva, 2018).

3. Fake News, Interreality, and the Social Operativity of Falsehood

In these new social conditions shaped by virtuality, it is important to dwell on the phenomenon of fake news and to see how digital space itself constitutes the condition of its existence. The phenomenon of fake news differs from classical disinformation or misinformation because, first of all, it is sustained by verisimilitude, itself grounded in the collection of user data and in pre-existing beliefs, which allows fake news to be constructed almost as if it were personalized and thus to become not true but socially real (Riva, 2018). Second, it finds fertile ground in the digital dimension of the Post-Truth era, where the margin within the dichotomous regime of true and false no longer fully subsists (Riva, 2018). Moreover, on social media, it is not even a priority to restore that margin, precisely because this is a space structured around entertainment (Riva, 2018).

In this regard, Riva argues that fake news is intertwined with two unprecedented phenomena arising from social virtuality, namely *interreality* and disintermediation (Riva, 2018). He calls *interreality* this new relational conjunction of online and offline, because what happens in the analog world can no longer be clearly separated from what happens in the virtual one (Riva, 2018); the two dimensions are intertwined and mutually conditioning. At the same time, *interreality* cannot be conceived apart from disintermediation, which consists in the social levelling that precisely constitutes digital “platforms” (Fabris, 2018; Riva, 2018). Institutions are absent from social media; what disappears in virtuality, then, are authorities (Riva, 2018). Yet, on the other hand, this also means that everyone may potentially acquire authoritativeness (Riva, 2018). One may think here of influencers and of the proliferation of self-styled coaches on social media, in areas such as fitness, emotional life, relationships, finance, and even mental well-being, where people may end up paying them in place of trained or licensed professionals. In light of this, fake news does not prioritize truth but factuality (Riva, 2018). On social media, fake news becomes a social fact through sharing and operativity. Fake news does not become truth, but social reality, and in this sense, it is interdependent with the other two phenomena (Riva, 2018).

It is precisely here that a Foucauldian reflection becomes especially useful. Social media seems to open a new and far more extensive freedom of expression: institutions appear to recede, and everyone may theoretically enjoy a discourse worthy of being heard and believed (Riva, 2018). But can one really say that the will to knowledge or verbal policing has disappeared (Foucault, 2009)? What happens when the regime of truth weakens, and when it is

no longer a priority to sanction what is to be legitimized as true and what is to be downgraded into the false (Foucault, 2009)? The issue, then, is not merely one of speaking but of being authorized, authoritative, and thus socially existent (Foucault, 2009). Women throughout history could obviously speak, yet their words lacked recognition, truth-status, and therefore power. The question is therefore not simply who can speak, but whose speech is allowed to count, namely to exist (Foucault, 2020). If one's words are denied value, credibility, and recognition, what is diminished is not only discourse, but the speaker's very standing as a socially recognizable subject (Butler, 2021).

4. Dominant Narration as a Violent Habit

The unprecedented narrative openness of social media consists precisely in the circulation of information; if such circulation degenerates into confusion, it may well entail a crisis of subjectivity, and society as well. In Arendtian terms, if in social media the regime of truth collapses, one might speak here of a collective depoliticization generated by a new form of equality, immense in scale, which flattens everything indiscriminately by erasing plurality (Arendt, 2018b). In other terms, if everyone can speak, words and speaking subjects may no longer carry the same value, and at that point, one could ask: how deep does this alienation run? Or perhaps another hypothesis is possible, namely that, before these unprecedented virtual spaces, deprived of physical points of reference, what occurs spontaneously is the reproduction and preservation of already embodied structures of power (Butler, 2021).

From this perspective, for instance, the proliferation of verbal violence on social media could mean a tentative attempt to restore order, that is, to re-establish what is already embodied, and taken to be right, to discard or marginalize what is wrong according to a familiar, customary, habitual *noesis* (Butler, 2021; Foucault, 2009, 2020). Following Arendt's reasoning, when she suggests that Nazi ideology emerged and exploded as the spontaneous consequence of an already existing predisposition, one may infer that massive consent is in some way bound to familiarity rather than estrangement, both emotional and theoretical, with regard to content (Arendt, 2018a). In other words, one tends to do what one already knows, especially in dark times, probably when fear reigns (Riva, 2025).

Indeed, social media operates through similarity: it caters to tastes and trends, immersing each user in a flow of related content and thereby creating communal spaces of mutual liking and self-complacency (Riva, 2018). This personalized mirror system provides a

space that is at once comfortable and easily irritated by difference (Riva, 2018). Since virtual capital is grounded in interaction, the system tends to reinforce dominant trends, or what could also be called habits of thought. In this sense, even personalization itself is mediated by a form of simplification that embraces a globalized and standardized knowledge (Reed et al., 2021; Riva, 2018, 2025).

Nor would it be surprising to find the persistence, repetition, and renewal of a dominant narration grounded in hateful thoughts whose genealogy is rooted in Ancient Greece (Levinas, 1979). Ideological structures such as racism, misogyny, and homophobia are not astonishing, since they belong to an established order of sense that has been built, transformed, and metabolized over millennia (Arendt, 2018a; Foucault, 2009; Guillaumin, 2010). And yet, the ideological force conferred by social media, namely its solidity and crystallization, is unprecedented. We must therefore ask how and why.

Today's historical conception concerns us directly, because it involves us both as acting subjects and as its very objects. The linguistic narration of events, that is, of what is happening among us and with us, our history in *toto*, ought to orient and clarify meaning, ought to form a stork (Blixen, 1937/1986), and yet with digitalization one encounters the opposite effect: confusion. Precisely because narration invests us directly and touches us in past, present, and future, it becomes legitimate to reflect on violence.

Verbal violence is often reduced to hate speech in the narrow sense, yet words wound in many ways, because language operates through human actions, and the human being lives in and inhabits meanings, which shape reality (Butler, 2021). Words, although abstract, are tangible because they happen among us, and as phenomena in act, they generate consequences and entail effects (Foucault, 1988, 2020). Social media, insofar as it is an expressive space, confirms the performativity of linguistic acts, and does so in an especially evident way through fake news, which shows how virtuality powerfully materializes "falsity" (Fabris, 2018).

Since social media is a narrative space, it is also crucial to reflect simultaneously on the narration of violence interwoven with a violent narrativity. This may help us observe how violence is internalized, normalized, and, at times, accepted. In the present wartime context, for instance, it should not be surprising if one has the impression of immobility, passivity, or indifference in the face of real distressing or cruel viral content showing oppressed peoples, such as Palestinians, asking for help (Yasmeen, 2024).

5. Objectification and the Digital Idea of the Body

Due to the relation between words and human existence, which is not discernible, it is worth going more deeply into the relation between narration, that is, the story of an alterity, and subjectivity on social media. Levinas becomes useful here because the problem is no longer only false representation, but the reduction of singular others to frames that absorb them before they can appear in their irreducibility.

Levinas criticized the European philosophical tradition by accusing it of having shed blood in the name of justice itself (Levinas, 1979). His denunciation of the metaphysics of the One, that is, of first philosophy, consists in the accusation of an immobile, egoic, narcissistic thought that has decreed what may be and what may not be (Levinas, 1979). Levinas brings to light the violence of a philosophy that has erased and absorbed every alterity into its relative negation: I and non-I (Levinas, 1979).

This movement of simplification and mirroring, described by Levinas, could also be traced in the very functioning of social media algorithms, which organize the flow of content through bubbles that erode confrontation and privilege radical dichotomies (Reed et al., 2021; Riva, 2018). What is thereby favoured is the circulation of what is already familiar, widely recognizable, and socially sedimented, giving rise to a viral vicious circle of sameness (Giansiracusa, 2021; Riva, 2018, 2025). Hateful content, moreover, is often amplified precisely because it provokes stronger reactions and therefore greater virality, feeding the accumulation of virtual capital (Giansiracusa, 2021; Riva, 2018).

Instead of the metaphysics of the One, Levinas proposes an otherwise, namely a metaphysical alternative that begins from ethics rather than ontology, that is, from the anonymity of being, because by placing the Face at the origin, there may spontaneously emerge care, openness, infinity rather than totality, and therefore humanity (Levinas, 1998). In the proximity, there is the awareness of having before oneself a vulnerable person, made of flesh and therefore mortal, like *me*, and infinitely other than *me* (Levinas, 1998). Levinas's thought strives to move beyond totality and thus beyond every comprehension-as-inclusion (Levinas, 1979, 1998). At the heart of metaphysical violence, he places the objectification of alterity, facilitated by the anonymity of being and by abstraction (Levinas, 1979).

From what has been said, the violence of indifference can also be observed on social media. Although it is a relational space, that is, a space full of Faces, it is possible to reflect on the complicity between the metaphysics of the One and the algorithms that shape digital

navigation (Giansiracusa, 2021; Levinas, 1979, 1998). Since social media is a space of entertainment, one may, in line with Levinas, underline a renewed objectification, this time more intense and more insidious, precisely because the Faces are there, yet they could be perceived as content. What now prevails might be an abstraction of persons: Faces are there, and yet they appear as abstractions, ideas of bodies. This, in turn, could nourish two reciprocal dynamics. On the one hand, there is the awareness of having power over the other person; on the other, there is the lightness of abstraction, namely the indifference, which de-responsibilizes and prevents one from fully grasping the weight of consequences for the Other.

6. Expropriated Narratives: Exposure, Closure, and Digital Violence

This ambivalence becomes especially visible in the media tribunal. There are different cases of this phenomenon, in which an enemy is collectively constructed. One particularly striking example is the case in which Trump unfoundedly accused Ruby Freeman and her daughter of having manipulated the vote in Biden's favour (Cheney & Gerstein, 2023). As a result, Freeman was overwhelmed by hate and threats, which forced her to change homes; nevertheless, she and her daughter lost the credibility attached to their work. Furthermore, even though she is now receiving justice, that is not enough to undo the false narrative imposed upon her dignity (Cheney & Gerstein, 2023). Recalling *interriality* (Riva, 2018), for perpetrators, there emerges the possibility of judging without being magistrates, an alluring occasion of power that includes punishment without full awareness, precisely because the other person remains distant, in the sense that they could be perceived as a character.

From this perspective, if such a reading is considered tenable, the body on social media does not disappear; rather, it becomes objectified into an idea of body, visible enough to be judged, attacked, exposed, and violated, yet not encountered enough to demand empathy, reciprocity, or responsibility. For instance, in order to observe even more clearly how the distinction between true and false narration becomes frighteningly irrelevant on social media, it is necessary to recall the phenomenon of pornographic deepfakes, particularly in the case of Grok, the AI chatbot on X (Schmitz-Berndt et al., 2026).

If a person is artificially denuded through AI and that image circulates online, the point is not exhausted by the fact that the image is false. Even if an institutional (analog) court later recognizes its falsity and grants justice, the social event is not undone. The correction may amend the fact, but it does not erase the event. That person has still been exposed, narrated from

outside, visually consumed, and publicly violated. What is at stake here is not only individual emotional harm, but the impossibility of fully defending one's identity at the social level. Voice, image, and recognizability are expropriated in ways that cannot be entirely restored. This has consequences far beyond the private sphere, affecting work, career, family relations, credibility, and the broader conditions under which a person is recognized by others. What appears here is a new totalizing expropriation whose novelty lies not in falsehood itself, but in the violent force with which falsehood becomes socially operative and historically consequential.

The loss of ownership in virtuality, namely of one's own history and thus of one's own existence, has an unprecedented force and novelty because it eludes reappropriation, legitimate self-defense, and recovery. The logic of the One remains the same, yet totalization acquires a different scale (Levinas, 1979). From this perspective, one can see how algorithms absorb our habits and embodied discourses, and thus could appear as the perfect evolution, the extreme realization, of the metaphysics of the One.

In other words, in these examples, digital falsehood does not merely misrepresent; it imposes a narrative that becomes real through circulation. Once seen, shared, and judged, the false image or accusation becomes an event that cannot be fully undone. Its violence lies in this closure: the subject is fixed within a story told from outside, while their own voice can no longer fully reopen it. What is lost is not only truth, but the possibility of reappropriating one's own narrative.

What algorithms intensify is not merely exposure, but the automated repetition of already sedimented patterns of recognition and exclusion. In this sense, they can be read as extending the logic of sameness rather than interrupting it. If algorithms may be read as an intensified realization of the metaphysics of the One, then dominant narration has not disappeared but has found new conditions of force, diffusion, and operativity. Its blindness is violent not only because it ignores alterity as such in its irreducibility, but also because, by doing so, it reduces singular subjects to consumable objects and thereby empties subjectivity itself. Nor does it clarify the world it claims to describe. On the contrary, it obscures it, making the present harder to read and leaving subjects less able to understand where they stand and how to move forward.

7. Toward a Historical Legibility beyond the True/False Dichotomy

Through the examples discussed in this article, from Trump's generative political propaganda to media tribunals and AI pornographic deepfakes, one may begin to see how narration operates in digital environments and how this may be reshaping our contemporary conception of history. The problem of confusion, then, may not be primarily epistemological. Falsehood has always existed; what seems to be at stake today is the growing possibility for narratives to become socially operative even when detached from the embodied and biographical traces through which lives become historically legible. Here, the stork is directly created, no longer the outcome of a reading; on social media, narration may impose itself with a flattened script, without interpretive distance. Confusion, then, may arise from this closure, from this blindness, from the disappearance of reading itself, from the loss of that free space of interpretation through which lives remain readable. If past footprints can no longer be read, one no longer knows where to place one's next step.

What appears here is not a neutral transformation, but a potentially violent one. The long habit of totalizing alterity within the European tradition could be seen as finding in digital architectures a new scale and intensity, as subjects become increasingly exposed to objectifying narrations that overwrite experience and close it within definitions. In this sense, on social media, there is no longer a clear distinction between true and false, nor is restoring that dichotomy even the priority, since virtuality has by now become real. If social media appear to promise narrative openness, such openness cannot be assumed as already given. It must instead be critically cultivated, so that digital narration may tend toward description rather than harden into definition (Cavarero, 1997). The issue, then, concerns not only misrepresentation but expropriation.

Reflecting along the lines opened by McLuhan in *Understanding Media*, this difficulty becomes clearer (McLuhan, 1964/2013). If «the medium is the message», this means that a medium does not merely transmit content, but reshapes the form, scale, and rhythm of human perception and relation (McLuhan, 1964/2013). As extensions of the human senses and faculties, digital technologies create environments in which life, perception, and relation are intensified and condensed (McLuhan, 1964/2013). Social media, then, do not simply host narratives: they are constituted by intrinsic logics of acceleration, visibility, repetition, personalization, and virality (McLuhan, 1964/2013; Riva, 2018). Since these environments are inhabited from within, their effects may remain opaque and overwhelming before they are fully

understood (McLuhan, 1964/2013). For this reason, the movement from definition toward description cannot be imagined as a simple correction of use but requires a critical awareness of the medium itself.

This article seeks to rethink, beyond the dichotomy true-false, our contemporary conception of history, while also inviting reflection on how technology might be engaged in ways that inaugurate genuinely new habits, rather than simply reproducing older ones in altered forms (Riva, 2025). Otherwise, we may continue to move forward while doing the same things, only differently.

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